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Title

Postural Stability in Osteoarthritis of the Knee and Hip: Analysis of Association with Pain Catastrophizing and Fear-Avoidance Beliefs.

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1 **Title**

2 **Postural Stability in Osteoarthritis of the Knee and Hip: Analysis of Association**
3 **with Pain Catastrophizing and Fear-Avoidance Beliefs.**

4

5 **ABSTRACTS FOR ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLES:**

6 **Background:** Population with knee OA are at risk of suffering sensations of instability,
7 and experience buckling. The instability has been associated with psychosocial
8 dysfunction, such as fear of movement, and impaired physical functioning. A high
9 degree of fear of movement is positive correlated with avoidance in other conditions.

10 **Objective:** To evaluate the relationship between postural stability, the degree of pain
11 catastrophizing, and fear avoidance beliefs in subjects with knee and hip osteoarthritis
12 (OA).

13 **Design:** Descriptive, cross-sectional study.

14 **Setting:** Four primary healthcare centers.

15 **Subjects:** 80 subjects with knee or combined knee and hip OA.

16 **Interventions:** Not applicable.

17 **Main outcome measurements:** Postural stability was evaluated using the Multi-
18 Directional Functional Reach Test (MDFRT), and a battery of self-reports was used to
19 assess the other following aspects: pain catastrophizing (pain catastrophizing scale),
20 fear-avoidance beliefs (Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia [TSK-11] and the Fear-
21 Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire), pain (visual analogue scale), disability (Western
22 Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index [WOMAC]), and self-efficacy
23 (Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale [CPSS]).

24 **Results:** The correlation analysis showed that scores on the MDFRT were negatively
25 associated with scores on the TSK-11 for activity avoidance ($r = -0.54$; $P < .001$) and

26 positively associated with the scores on the CPSS for coping ($r = 0.59$; $P < .001$). The
27 scores for the MDFRT to the right and the total WOMAC were negatively associated (r
28 $= -0.61$, $P < .001$). The scores for the MDFRT to the left were positively associated with
29 the CPSS scores for coping ($r = 0.64$, $P < .001$). The scores for the MDFRT forward
30 were predicted by CPSS and TSK-11 scores (28.9% of variance) as well as activity
31 avoidance, avoidance of physical activity, helplessness (34.7% of variance), and CPSS
32 pain coping (34.3% of variance).

33 **Conclusions:** These findings suggest that pain catastrophizing and fear-avoidance
34 beliefs are related with postural stability in subjects with knee and hip OA. Postural
35 stability is negatively correlated with pain catastrophizing and TSK activity avoidance.
36 Thus, based on these results, psychosocial factors should be taken into consideration in
37 the assessment and treatment of patients with hip and knee OA.

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52 INTRODUCTION

53 Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most prevalent diagnosed joint disorder in adults worldwide
54 [1]. This condition is one of most reported reasons for visits to primary care centers,
55 especially in adults between 45 and 65 years of age [2]. The main anatomical sites
56 affected by OA are the vertebrae, knees, hands, and hip [3]. Quintana et al. described
57 the prevalence of symptomatic knee OA as 12.2%; moreover, the prevalence is
58 significantly higher in women (14.9%) than men (8.7%) and tends to increase by 12%
59 with each year of age [4].

60

61 Pathophysiologically, OA is the result of the degenerative process of articular cartilage
62 and the formation of new bone matrix that can be assessed radiologically [5]. Pain in
63 OA has multifactorial etiologies. Nociceptive and neuropathic mechanisms appear to be
64 involved and mediated by peripheral and central processes [6]. A recent study suggested
65 that central sensitization processes of pain are present in cases of moderate to severe
66 symptomatology [7]. Furthermore, it has been suggested that central processes are
67 strongly influenced by biological and psychosocial factors [6].

68

69 It has been observed that pain catastrophizing has been associated with increasing
70 physical disability [8], increased pain [8], and low self-efficacy [9]. Importantly, OA
71 processes can affect proprioception [10] and postural stability [11], which can also lead

72 to decreased balance, thereby increasing the risk of falling mainly during dynamic
73 activities [12,13]. Recent evidence demonstrated the role of muscle weakness and
74 chronic pain as elements that decrease balance and alter postural stability, which also
75 increase this risk [13]. The risk of falling has become a critical public health problem
76 and can lead to significant limitations and a significant decrease in quality of life in
77 patients with OA [14].

78

79 Research estimates that 27% of the population with knee OA are at risk of suffering
80 sensations of instability, and 18% actually experience buckling [15]. Cases of instability
81 with or without falling were associated with psychosocial dysfunction, such as fear of
82 movement, and impaired physical functioning [15]. In addition, negative psychosocial
83 factors, especially fear of movement, have an adverse impact on pain and disability in
84 patients with OA [16–20]. In fact, a high degree of fear of movement is positively
85 correlated with avoidance when patients with chronic low back pain perform simple
86 movements [21]. This fear of movement and avoidance could be acquired over time
87 through repeated painful stimulus [22]. Thus, this information leads us to propose as our
88 main hypothesis that various psychosocial factors mainly related to a fear-avoidance
89 model have important implications in the balance and stability of patients with OA of
90 the hip and knee.

91

92 The primary objective of this study was to examine the degree of pain catastrophizing
93 and fear avoidance beliefs as well as their relationship with postural stability in people
94 with hip/knee OA. A secondary objective was to examine which psychosocial factors
95 could serve as predictors of postural stability.

96

97 METHODS

98

99 Study Design

100 This research is a descriptive, cross-sectional study using non-probability sampling.
101 One researcher administered the participant appointments and self-report
102 questionnaires, while two physiotherapists, with two and 10 years of experience (AST,
103 RFP), were responsible for collecting all measurements. After receiving detailed
104 information about the study, the volunteers gave their written informed consent. The
105 physician who diagnosed all of the participating subjects with OA performed the
106 informed consent process with one of the researchers present in the room. All of the
107 procedures used in this study conformed with the ethical norms of the Helsinki
108 Declaration and were approved by the local ethics committee of XXXXXXXXXXXX.
109 The reporting of the study follows “Strengthening the Reporting of Observational
110 studies in Epidemiology” (STROBE) [23].

111

112 Subjects

113 A non-probability sample of volunteer subjects with OA was recruited from four
114 primary healthcare centers in XXXX. These four centers belong to the national public
115 health system in _____ and provide services mainly to an urban population. Subjects
116 were eligible for the study if 1) they reported bilateral knee pain or combined bilateral
117 knee and hip pain for at least the prior three months, 2) they met the American College
118 of Rheumatology criteria for knee and hip OA [24], and 3) there was radiographic
119 evidence of OA affecting their knees or combined knees and hips. Subjects were
120 recruited from November of 2013 to June of 2014. A family physician confirmed the
121 diagnosis of knee and hip OA through subjective patient histories, clinical

122 examinations, and radiographic findings. The study physician graded individual
123 radiographic features of OA using radiological standard images and the Kellgren-
124 Lawrence criteria [25]. Exclusion criteria were indications other than primary
125 osteoarthritis (e.g., post-traumatic; rheumatoid arthritis) [26].

126

127 **Data Collection**

128 After consenting to the study, the recruited subjects were given a battery of
129 questionnaires to complete. These included various self-reports for demographic and
130 pain-related information. Participants were verbally given standardized instructions;
131 moreover, these instructions were repeated on the questionnaires (e.g., the number of
132 questions on the questionnaire, the questionnaire was printed on both sides of the page,
133 and the purpose of the questionnaire). The sociodemographic questionnaire contained
134 questions on the following information: gender, date of birth, marital status, living
135 arrangements, educational level, and work status. Measures of pain catastrophizing were
136 assessed using the Pain Catastrophizing Scale (PCS), and fear of movement was
137 measured using the validated Spanish versions of the Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia
138 (TSK-11). Fear-avoidance beliefs were quantified using the Fear-Avoidance Beliefs
139 Questionnaire (FABQ), and pain intensity was measured using a Visual Analogue Scale
140 (VAS). Physical disability information was collected using the Western Ontario and
141 McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index (WOMAC), and self-efficacy was collected
142 using the validated Spanish version of the Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale (CPSS).
143 Once subjects completed all of the questionnaires, the physiotherapist proceeded to
144 evaluate their stability using the Multi-Directional Functional Reach Test (MDFRT).

145

146 **Postural Stability**

147 The MDFRT evaluates the limits of postural stability in three directions (i.e., forward,
148 lateral right, and left) [27]. The measurement is obtained through the displacement
149 reached by the patient (cm) by shifting the center of gravity to the limits of the base of
150 support, while the feet remain stationary. A yardstick was mounted on the wall and
151 adjusted to the height of each participant's acromion, and the excursion of the distal tip
152 of the third digit was recorded. The start and end positions of the finger of the
153 outstretched hand were recorded, and the difference represented the total reach for a
154 particular direction. Participants were instructed to lean as far forward (or to the right or
155 left) as possible without lifting their heels or losing their balance. The participants stood
156 with their heels 10 cm apart and each foot angled at 15°. Participants were given
157 instructions on how to perform each test and asked if they understood the directions.
158 The participants were also informed that the tests would not begin until they felt ready
159 to perform the task.

160

161 Three trials were performed for each test with a 3 minute rest between each trial. The
162 average of the 3 trials in each direction was used in the subsequent analyses. Evaluators
163 stood in close proximity to the subjects during the MDFRT to ensure the safety of the
164 participants. The MDFRT has been shown to have good intra-rater, inter-rater, and test-
165 retest reliability in older adults [27].

166

167 **Self-reported Clinical Assessments**

168

169 - *Pain Catastrophizing*

170 The Spanish version of the PCS assesses the degree to which the participant engages in
171 pain catastrophizing [28]. The PCS contains 13 items and the following three-factor

172 structure: rumination, magnification, and helplessness. Each item is rated using a 5-
173 point Likert scale, i.e., from 0 (not at all) to 4 (all the time). The theoretical scoring
174 range is between 0 and 52, with lower scores indicating less catastrophizing. The PCS
175 has been demonstrated to have acceptable psychometric properties (internal consistency,
176 $\alpha=.84$) [28].

177

178 - *Fear-avoidance Beliefs*

179 The Spanish version of the TSK-11 is a self-reported questionnaire that assesses fear of
180 re-injury due to movement [29]. Total TSK-11 scores range from 11 to 44 points, and
181 each item is scored using a four-point Likert scale (i.e., 1 = strongly disagree to 4 =
182 strongly agree). The higher scores indicate greater fear of pain, movement, and
183 injury. The TSK-11 has a two-factor structure of activity avoidance and harm and has
184 been demonstrated to have acceptable psychometric properties (internal consistency,
185 $\alpha=.78$) [29].

186

187 The FABQ consists of 16 items divided into two subscales [30]. Each item is scored on
188 a seven-point Likert scale (i.e., 0 = strongly disagree to 6 = strongly agree). The FABQ
189 evaluates patient beliefs about the effect of physical activity (FABQ-PA) and work
190 (FABQ-W) on their experience of pain. A high score signified high fear avoidance. The
191 Spanish version of the FABQ has been demonstrated to have acceptable psychometric
192 properties (internal consistency, $\alpha=.93$) [30]. The wording was changed to reference
193 lower extremity disability for the purposes of this study. Preliminary data regarding the
194 psychometric properties of the modified FABQ were collected.

195

196 - *Pain Intensity*

197 Pain intensity was measured with the VAS, which consists of a 100-mm line on which
198 the subjects place a mark representing their pain intensity between the left side
199 representing “no pain” and the right side representing “the worst pain imaginable.” The
200 VAS has been found to be a reliable measure of pain (intra-class correlation coefficient
201 [ICC]= 0.95) [31].

202

203 - *Disability*

204 The WOMAC questionnaire was used for the measurement of disability in people with
205 OA [32]. It consists of 24 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale divided into three
206 subscales (i.e., pain, stiffness, and physical function). The Spanish version of the
207 WOMAC questionnaire has been demonstrated to have acceptable psychometric
208 properties (internal consistency, α = range .81 to .93) [32].

209

210 - *Self-efficacy*

211 Self-efficacy was assessed using the Spanish version of the CPSS [33]. The scale was
212 developed to measure perceived self-efficacy and ability to cope with the consequences
213 of pain in chronic pain subjects. The Spanish version of this scale contains 19 items and
214 three domains that assess self-efficacy for pain management, physical functioning, and
215 coping symptoms. CPSS total scores are obtained by adding patient responses on each
216 item, and higher scores indicate greater self-efficacy for managing pain. The Spanish
217 version of the CPSS has been demonstrated to have acceptable psychometric properties
218 (internal consistency, α =.91) [33].

219

220 **Sample Size**

221 The sample size was estimated using G*Power 3.1.7 for Windows (G*Power© from
222 University of Dusseldorf, Germany) [34]. More specifically, the sample size was
223 calculated using linear multiple regression (i.e., fixed model with R^2 deviation from
224 zero), which permitted a power calculation to detect the predictors (i.e., pain-related and
225 psychological measures) of the postural stability measures (i.e., the MDFRT scores). A
226 medium effect size of 0.20 was used to obtain 80% statistical power (1- β error
227 probability) with an α error level probability of .05. The number of predictors selected
228 was 7. Ultimately, we estimated that a total of 80 subjects would be required for this
229 study. For the regression analysis, we also considered and applied the rule of 10 cases
230 per variable to obtain reasonably stable estimates for the regression coefficients [35].

231

232 **Data Analysis**

233 All data analyses were performed on SPSS for Windows, Version 21.0 (SPSS Inc.,
234 Chicago, IL) with an α level of .05. Descriptive statistics were generated for the
235 sociodemographic data, psychological data, pain-related data, and MDFRT measures
236 (i.e., MDFRT forward, MDFRT right, and MDFRT left). The continuous variables are
237 presented as means \pm standard deviation (SD) and ranges, and the categorical variables
238 are presented as absolute numbers and relative frequency (i.e., percentages). The
239 normality of the data was evaluated using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test. The VAS,
240 TSK-11, PSC, and FABQ-W measures did not meet the normal distribution. However, a
241 normal distribution for all variables was assumed according to the central limit theorem.
242 This theorem states that the distribution of the average of a large number of independent
243 variables (i.e., a large sample size is considered from 30 to 50 or more subjects) will be
244 approximately normal regardless of the underlying distribution [36,37].

245 The basic psychometric analysis of the internal consistency of each of the self-reports
246 was assessed with Cronbach's α . For self-reports to be internally consistent, the α levels
247 should be above .7 [38]. An analysis of the intra-rater reliability for measurements for
248 MDFRT was conducted using the ICC. The standard error of measurement (SEM) and
249 the minimum detectable change at the 90% confidence level (MDC_{90}) were also
250 calculated for this variable. Reliability levels were defined based on the following
251 classification: good reliability – $ICC \geq 0.75$. moderate reliability – $ICC \geq 0.50$ and $<$
252 0.75 , and poor reliability – < 0.40 [39].

253 In order to compare the outcomes between subjects who had only knee OA against
254 those who had OA of the knee and hip, a Student's t-test for independent samples was
255 used.

256 The relationship between the MDFRT measures and the self-reports for pain-related and
257 psychological measures was examined using Pearson's correlation coefficients. Multiple
258 linear regression analysis was performed to estimate the strength of the associations
259 between the results of MDFRT forward (model 1), MDFRT right (model 2), and
260 MDFRT left (model 3) (criterion variables). Psychological and pain-related variables
261 were used as predictor variables. Regression analysis was replicated three times using
262 the following criterion variables of multidirectional stability measures as predictors: 1)
263 all variables, 2) variables related to fear-avoidance and pain, and 3) variables related to
264 pain and functional capacity analysis.

265

266 Variance inflation factors (VIFs) were calculated to detect the presence of any multi-
267 collinearity issues in any of the three models. The strength of association was examined
268 using regression coefficients (β), P values, and adjusted R^2 . Standardized beta
269 coefficients were reported for each predictor variable included in the final reduced

270 models to allow for the direct comparison between the predictor variables in the
271 regression model and the criterion variables being studied.

272

273 **RESULTS**

274 A total of 94 subjects with knee OA or combined knee and hip OA met the inclusion
275 criteria. Fourteen of these subjects refused to participate in the study; therefore, the final
276 study sample consisted of a total of 80 participants (i.e., 64 females and 16 males).
277 Among the subjects included in the study, 47 presented only knee OA, and 33 presented
278 knee OA combined with hip OA. The baseline sociodemographic, psychological, and
279 pain-related characteristics of the sample are summarized in Tables 1 and 2. The
280 comparative analysis results showed no differences in the psychological and pain-
281 related measures of subjects with knee OA and that of those with combined knee and
282 hip OA ($P>.05$). Nevertheless, we did observe statistically significant differences in the
283 postural stability measures and physical function of subjects with knee OA as compared
284 to that of subjects with knee and hip OA (Table 2).

285 The internal consistency of all of the self-reports was good or excellent (PCS, $\alpha=.94$;
286 TSK-11, $\alpha=.84$; FABQ, $\alpha=.92$; WOMAC, $\alpha=.96$; CPSS, $\alpha=.93$), and the reliability
287 levels of the MDFRT measures were good. The descriptive statistics, ICCs, and the
288 associated 95% CI, SEMs, and MDC of the assessment intra-raters are presented in
289 Table 3.

290

291 **Correlations Analysis**

292 Table 4 contains the results of the correlation analyses examining the bivariate
293 relationships among MDFRT measures and the self-reports for pain-related and
294 psychological measures. The MDFRT forward was negatively associated with the TSK

295 scores related to activity avoidance ($r = -0.54$; $P < .001$) and positively associated with the
296 CPSS scores related to coping ($r = 0.59$; $P < .001$). As expected, MDFRT right and total
297 WOMAC scores were negatively associated ($r = -0.61$; $P < .001$). The MDFRT were
298 positively associated with the CPSS scores related to coping ($r = 0.64$; $P < .001$). The
299 associations between psychological factors were not strong; therefore, excessive
300 collinearity was expected in the planned regression models.

301

302 **Multiple Linear Regression Analysis**

303 A linear regression analysis was performed to evaluate contributors to the MDFRT
304 forward, MDFRT right, and MDFRT left measures and the self-reports for the pain-
305 related and psychological measures in the subjects with knee and hip OA. The results
306 are presented in Tables 5 through 7. Furthermore, the VIFs for the regression models
307 (Tables 5-7) were sufficiently low to satisfy the multicollinearity assumption of multiple
308 regressions.

309

310 In the first model, the criterion variable of MDFRT forward was predicted by self-
311 efficacy and kinesiophobia (all variables analysis), explaining 28.9% of the variance. It
312 was also predicted by activity avoidance, avoidance of physical activity, and
313 helplessness (i.e., variables related to fear-avoidance analysis), explaining 34.7% of the
314 variance. Finally, it was also predicted by coping (i.e., the variable related to pain and
315 functional capacity analysis), explaining 34.3% of variance (Tables 5-7).

316

317 In the second model, the criterion variable of MDFRT right was predicted by disability
318 (all variables analysis), explaining 37.9% of variance, by activity avoidance and
319 helplessness (i.e., among variables related to fear-avoidance analysis), explaining 31.5%

320 of the variance, and by physical function (i.e., among the variables related with pain and
321 functional capacity analysis), explaining 31.7% of the variance (Tables 5-7).

322

323 In the third model, the criterion variable MDFRT left was predicted by self-efficacy and
324 fear avoidance (all variables analysis), explaining 36.9% of the variance, by activity
325 avoidance and helplessness (i.e., among the variables related fear-avoidance analysis),
326 explaining 29% of the variance, and by physical function and coping (i.e., among the
327 variables related with pain and functional capacity analysis), explaining 42.4% of the
328 variance (Tables 5-7).

329

330 **DISCUSSION**

331 The present study was designed to build an understanding of the relationship of fear
332 avoidance beliefs and pain catastrophizing with postural stability in subjects with hip
333 and knee OA. The findings of this study increase the knowledge about the involvement
334 of psychosocial factors in the postural stability of patients with knee and hip OA.
335 Current evidence has shown the influence of psychosocial factors on pain and function
336 in patients with OA [9,17,19,40]. The results in the present study support the proposed
337 hypothesis and show that disability and fear-avoidance beliefs were negatively
338 correlated with postural stability data measured by the MDFRT. Moreover, the role of
339 self-efficacy was positively correlated with the results of the postural stability. The
340 results of this investigation partly agree with previous studies [17,19,40].

341

342 **Postural Stability and Fear-avoidance Beliefs**

343 The fear-avoidance model proposes that pain perception is primarily influenced by pain-
344 related fear and pain catastrophizing [41]. High levels of pain-related fear and pain

345 catastrophizing are associated with an avoidance behavioral response, which is believed
346 to be a precursor to developing a chronic disability [41]. In our results, no statistically
347 significant differences were observed in the comparison of the variables related to the
348 fear-avoidance model among subjects with OA of the knee and hip as compared to
349 subjects with OA of the knee. According to our results, the anatomical change of those
350 specific regions of the lower extremity do not significantly influence the psychological
351 and pain-related variables, but postural stability and functional capacity do have a
352 significant influence on the variables related to the fear avoidance model. In the
353 multiple regression analysis, this study has identified that fear-avoidance (i.e., the TSK-
354 11 and the FABQ) is an important predictor of postural stability, and when variables
355 related to the fear-avoidance model were analyzed, it was identified that activity
356 avoidance, avoidance of physical activity, and helplessness were the most important
357 predictors of postural stability.

358

359 These results suggest that fear-avoidance factors are significant from the perspective of
360 the analysis of postural stability in subjects with knee and/or hip OA. This is in
361 accordance with previous scientific evidence related to fear-avoidance factors with other
362 functional aspects. In a sample of 254 patients, Heuts et al. [17] observed that pain was
363 associated with higher levels of fear of movement and lower levels of daily functioning.
364 Moreover, in another study, fear of movement explained 40% of functional impairment
365 [17]. In addition, Somers et al. [19] showed that the fear of pain explains 7% of
366 psychological disability and 5% of the gait disturbance. A systematic review showed
367 that fear of falling was associated with at least one fall, older age, and the female gender
368 [42]. The influence of fear of pain on functional alterations in other chronic conditions,
369 such as back pain, has also been described [43]. Other studies have also found that fear-

370 related pain is significantly associated with functional limitations [17] and with the
371 ability to walk at a normal, intermediate, or high speed [19]. In relation to this, Belo et
372 al. [44] observed that fear of movement was associated with persistent knee pain.

373

374 Of the three subscales of the PCS, the results of this study show that the helplessness
375 subscale provided the more relevant results and a greater association with postural
376 stability. Another study also showed that catastrophic helplessness is a predictor of pain
377 interference and depression [45]. Moreover, previous research has described that pain
378 catastrophizing is one of the constructs that has a more negative impact on patients with
379 OA [40]. Along these lines, in patients with OA, Shelby et al. [9] found that pain
380 catastrophizing is associated with higher levels of pain and disability and lower levels of
381 self-efficacy.

382

383 **Postural Stability, Disability, and Self-efficacy**

384 The findings of this study show that pain coping and physical functioning are predictors
385 of postural stability. Additionally, pain coping self-efficacy, which is a subscale that
386 was positively associated with physical functioning, had a negative association. These
387 results are interesting, considering that low functionality elements are associated with
388 postural stability [14], instability in the knee [15], and gait speed [46]. Moreover, recent
389 scientific evidence has shown that self-efficacy is associated with a significantly
390 decreased gait speed [47], but high levels of self-efficacy are associated with a better
391 prognosis for recovery [48].

392

393 Furthermore, it has been indicated that variation in the parameters of motion perception
394 is strongly influenced by the physical disability but not by the radiographic findings

395 themselves [46]. Several studies have investigated the stability (i.e., either static or
396 dynamic) in OA [11–13,15]. Some of the important clinical signs and symptoms of OA
397 are joint pain, weakness, loss of function, activity limitation, and psychosocial
398 impairment (e.g., fear avoidance behaviors or fear of pain), all of which can result in
399 increased disability and a lower quality of life [10,13,17,46,49].

400

401 **Clinical Implications**

402 These results could have implications in clinical practice. The measurement used to
403 evaluate the postural stability presents good reliability values (ICC=0.89 to 0.96).
404 Although previous studies have reported that the MDFRT has good reliability [27,50],
405 this is the first study to use this test in subjects with knee and hip OA. The authors
406 consider the MDFRT to be an inexpensive and simple test to perform; moreover, it
407 could easily be implemented into clinical practice. The results of this study show an
408 influence of fear-avoidance factors on postural stability in subjects with OA of the hip
409 and knee, which is why the authors believe that psychosocial factors should be taken
410 into consideration in the diagnosis and treatment planning for these patients. The
411 approach of therapeutic exercise interventions in combination with therapeutic
412 education programs could be used as part of the treatment plan for reducing fear-
413 avoidance beliefs in patients with OA of the hip and knee. Scientific evidence indicates
414 that these interventions increase the level of self-efficacy [51], which is a prognostic
415 factor to improve pain outcomes in OA. [48].

416

417 From a clinical point of view, the reduction of physical function in patients with OA of
418 the knee can alter proprioception of an asymptomatic knee [10], and a proprioceptive
419 deficit could affect the postural stability of the hip and knee. Promoting pain-coping

420 skills and strategies that reduce fear avoidance beliefs [52] and encouraging the
421 performance of supervised therapeutic exercise programs can improve proprioception.
422 According Knoop et al. [10], proprioception is a modifiable factor, and we must
423 consider that increased physical activity is associated with improved functional
424 performance and reduced disability [53].

425

426 **Limitations**

427 The first limitation of this study is that we carried out a non-probability sampling
428 method; therefore, we cannot extrapolate the results to the entire population of patients
429 with OA of the knee and hip. The second limitation is the lack of a control group, i.e., a
430 healthy subject's group with which we can compare results, thereby allowing us to
431 establish a base line of normal postural stability. Nevertheless, data obtained by Newton
432 [54] and Steffen and Mollinger [50] in healthy elderly patients (age=74.1±7.4 and
433 age=69±11, respectively) indicate that measures of postural stability according
434 MDFRT are better (MDFRT forward= 22.58 cm and MDFRT forward= 29 cm,
435 respectively) than those obtained in this study, thereby indicating a possible disorder in
436 postural stability in the assessed patients in the present study (MDFRT forward=19.53
437 cm).

438 Another important limitation of this study is that the exclusion criteria only considered
439 patients with trauma or secondary OA; hence, we did not provide any control for other
440 disorders that could produce pain or disability, such as neuropathic pain, weakness, or
441 decreased range of motion. Individuals with OA have structural alterations and
442 abnormal patterns of muscle activation [55], but the present study did not examine these
443 variables. The number of falls suffered was not assessed, which can be considered a

444 major limitation since this parameter is associated with the patient's functionality,
445 quality of life, and other psychosocial aspects [15].

446

447 **CONCLUSION**

448 A moderate relationship was observed between postural stability and fear-avoidance
449 beliefs in patients with knee and hip OA. Postural stability is negatively correlated with
450 pain catastrophizing and TSK activity avoidance. Future longitudinal studies are needed
451 to demonstrate whether fear-avoidance beliefs influence the evolution of postural
452 stability.

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Table 1. Descriptive statistics for sociodemographic variables ($n=80$).

Variable	N (%)	Mean (SD)	(Min- max)
Age (years)	80	67.44 ± 9.908	(50- 85)
Height (cm)	80	159.17 ± 8.30	(145- 181)
Weight (Kg)	80	74.43 ± 15.00	(48- 128)
Pain duration (months)	80	77.48 ± 53.77	(6- 240)
Gender			
Male	16 (20.00%)		
Female	64 (80.00%)		
Marital status			
Single	5 (6.30%)		
Married	60 (75.00%)		
Divorced	4 (5.00%)		
Widower	11 (13.80%)		
Occupation			
Active	22 (27.50%)		
Unemployed	6 (7.50%)		
Retired	52 (65.00%)		
Sick leave	0 (0.00%)		
Education			
None	13 (16.30%)		
Primary	35 (43.80%)		
Secondary	24 (30.00%)		
University	8 (10.00%)		

Abbreviations: SD, Standard Deviation

Table 2. Comparative and descriptive statistics for psychological, and pain-related variables ($n=80$)

	Total Sample Size (n=80)	Knee OA (n=47)	Knee and Hip OA (n=33)	Comparison between groups
Variable	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	P Value
MDFRT forward (cm)	19.53 ± 6.24	21.6±5.96	16.57±5.45	.001
MDFRT lateral right (cm)	17.51 ± 5.53	19.01±5.06	15.36±5.07	.003
MDFRT lateral left (cm)	17.53 ± 5.44	18.83±5.37	15.69±5.08	.01
VAS (mm)	51.94 ± 21.78	48.06±21.43	57.28±21.44	.07
TSK-11	29.09 ± 7.78	27.72±8.01	31.03±7.11	.06
- Activity avoidance	18.46 ± 5.71	17.61±5.69	19.66±5.61	.11
- Harm	10.62 ± 3.13	10.1±3.26	11.36±2.82	.07
PCS	15.39 ± 12.55	15.13±13.23	15.76±11.72	.82
- Helplessness	6.92 ± 6.08	6.53±6.04	7.48±5.63	.49
- Magnification	3.25 ± 2.76	3.40±3.02	3.03±2.37	.55
- Rumination	5.18 ± 4.64	5.15±4.65	5.21±4.71	.95
WOMAC	57.06 ± 18.83	54.38±19.11	60.88±18.02	.13
- Pain	12.03 ± 4.08	11.55±4.26	12.7±3.77	.22
- Stiffness	4.84 ± 1.89	4.55±1.77	5.24±2.01	.11
- Physical function	40.82 ± 14.38	38.02±14.24	44.76±13.84	.04
FABQ	38.49 ± 23.52	35.5±24.08	42.66±22.39	.18
- Physical activity	18.76 ± 9.49	17.53±9.99	20.51±8.56	.16
- Work	19.60 ± 16.38	17.76±16.03	22.15±16.76	.24
CPSS	133.00 ± 35.87	139.04±37.66	124.39±31.76	.72
- Pain control	55.76 ± 16.03	57.89±16.71	52.73±15.57	.15
- Coping	48.46 ± 13.12	50.89±12.66	45±13.18	.05
- Functionality	28.78 ± 11.90	30.26±12.81	26.67±10.3	.18

Abbreviations: VAS, Visual Analogue Scale; TSK-11, Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia; PCS, Pain Catastrophizing Scale; WOMAC, Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index; FABQ, Fear-Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire; CPSS, Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; SD, standard deviation.

Table 3. Intra-rater reliability and descriptive statistics for MDFRT measurements in knee and hip osteoarthritis patients.

Measures	Mean \pm SD	3 minutes between trials (Trial 1-Trial 3)			
		ICC	95% CI for ICC	SEM	MDC ₉₀
MDFRT forward (cm)	19.53 \pm 6.24	0.95	0.92 – 0.96	1.42	3.31
MDFRT lateral right (cm)	17.51 \pm 5.53	0.96	0.95 to 0.97	1.01	2.37
MDFRT lateral left (cm)	17.53 \pm 5.44	0.89	0.85 to 0.92	1.83	4.28

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; ICC, intraclass correlation coefficient; MDFRT, multi directional functional reach test; MDC₉₀, minimal detectable change at the 90% confidence level; SD, standard deviation; SEM, standard error of the measurement.

Table 4. Pearson's correlation coefficient between variables analyzed in the study.

	MDFRT forward	MDFRT right	MDFRT left
VAS (mm)	-0.310**	-0.196	-0.249*
TSK-11	-0.476**	-0.353**	-0.415**
Activity avoidance	-0.507**	-0.332**	-0.444**
Harm	-0.258*	-0.271*	-0.219
PCS	-0.283*	-0.481**	-0.401**
Helplessness	-0.327**	-0.549**	-0.452**
Magnification	-0.238*	-0.384**	-0.328**
Rumination	-0.197	-0.360**	-0.308**
WOMAC	-0.422**	-0.619**	-0.515**
Pain	-0.273*	-0.517**	-0.395**
Stiffness	-0.285*	-0.500**	-0.437**
Physical function	-0.474**	-0.567**	-0.545**
FABQ	-0.267*	-0.305**	-0.373**
Physical activity	-0.107	-0.232*	-0.262*
Work	-0.320**	-0.296**	-0.376**
CPSS	0.535**	0.489**	0.568**
Pain control	0.506**	0.377**	0.490**
Coping	0.595**	0.534**	0.641**
Functionality	0.277*	0.380**	0.347**

Abbreviations: MDFRT, Multi-Directional Functional Reach Test; VAS, Visual Analogue Scale; TSK, Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia; PCS, Pain Catastrophizing Scale; WOMAC, Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index; FABQ, Fear-Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire; CPSS, Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale.

* P<.05

** P<.01.

Table 5. Multiple linear regression analysis for all variables.

Criterion variable: MDFRT forward				
Overall Model $R^2=0.299$ Adjusted $R^2=0.289$ F= 31.068				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
CPSS	0.071	0.391	.001	1.375
TSK-11	-0.248	-0.298	.009	1.375
Excluded variables				
VAS (mm)	-	-0.140	.173	1.191
PCS	-	-0.082	.430	1.212
WOMAC	-	-0.188	.095	1.434
FABQ	-	-0.080	.450	1.263
Criterion variable: MDFRT right				
Overall Model $R^2=0.387$ Adjusted $R^2=0.379$ F= 46.137				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
WOMAC	-0.190	-0.622	.001	1.375
Excluded variables				
VAS (mm)	-	0.25	.800	1.125
TSK-11	-	-0.163	.093	1.120
PCS	-	0.008	.957	2.310
FABQ	-	-0.472	.638	1.273
CPSS	-	-.191	.081	1.429
Criterion variable: MDFRT left				
Overall Model $R^2=0.386$ Adjusted $R^2=0.369$ F= 22.620				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
CPSS	0.078	0.498	.001	1.054
FABQ	-0.065	-0.275	.005	1.054
Excluded variables				
VAS (mm)	-	-0.015	.886	1.182
TSK-11	-	-0.054	.653	1.647
PCS	-	-0.093	.403	1.418
WOMAC	-	-0.206	.090	1.729

Abbreviations: CPSS, Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale; FABQ, Fear-Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire; MDFRT, Multi-Directional Functional Reach Test; PCS, Pain Catastrophizing Scale; TSK, Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia; VAS, Visual Analogue Scale; WOMAC, Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index.

Table 6. Multiple linear regression analysis for variables related fear-avoidance.

Criterion variable: MDFRT forward				
Overall Model $R^2=0.381$ Adjusted $R^2=0.347$ F= 11.379				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
TSK-11-AA	-0.547	-0.500	.001	1.282
PCS-H	-0.271	-0.257	.014	1.261
FABQ-PA	0.252	0.380	.003	1.863
FABQ-W	-0.100	-0.260	.034	1.741
Excluded variables				
TSK-11-H	-	0.14	.895	1.350
PCS-M	-	0.22	.879	2.557
PCS-R	-	0.124	.453	3.189
Criterion variable: MDFRT right				
Overall Model $R^2=0.332$ Adjusted $R^2=0.315$ F= 18.910				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
PCS-H	-0.458	-0.492	.001	1.079
TSK-11-AA	-0.188	-0.195	.049	1.079
Excluded variables				
TSK-11-H	-	-0.095	.385	1.344
PCS-M	-	0.090	.550	2.522
PCS-R	-	0.233	.163	3.154
FABQ-PA	-	0.068	.542	1.409
FABQ-W	-	-0.038	.725	1.317
Criterion variables: MDFRT left				
Overall Model $R^2=0.308$ Adjusted $R^2=0.290$ F= 16.927				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
PCS-H	-0.321	-0.351	.001	1.079
TSK-11-AA	-0.329	-0.346	.001	1.079
Excluded variables				
TSK-11-H	-	0.039	.725	1.344
PCS-M	-	0.016	.918	2.522
PCS-R	-	0.088	.605	3.154
FABQ-PA	-	0.032	.781	1.403
FABQ-W	-	-0.137	.215	1.317

Abbreviations: FABQ-PA, Fear-Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire-Physical Activity; FABQ-W, FABQ-Work; MDFRT, Multi-Directional Functional Reach Test; PCS-H, Pain Catastrophizing Scale-Helplessness; PCS-M, PCS-Magnification; PCS-R, PCS-Rumination; TSK-11-AA, Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia-11-Activity avoidance; TSK-11-H, TSK-11-Harm.

Table 7. The multiple linear regression analysis for variables related with pain and functional capacity.

Criterion variable: MDFRT forward				
Overall Model $R^2=0.352$ Adjusted $R^2=0.343$ F= 40.147				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
CPSS-C	0.286	0.593	.001	1.000
Excluded variables				
VAS (mm)	-	-0.112	.265	1.146
WOMAC-P	-	0.044	.692	1.377
WOMAC-S	-	-0.017	.874	1.256
WOMAC-PF	-	-0.171	.182	1.859
CPSS-PC	-	0.177	.184	2.018
CPSS-F	-	-0.096	.405	1.500
Criterion variable: MDFRT right				
Overall Model $R^2=0.326$ Adjusted $R^2=0.317$ F= 35.780				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
WOMAC-PF	-0.227	-0.571	.001	1.000
Excluded variables				
VAS (mm)	-	0.043	.682	1.197
WOMAC-P	-	-0.141	.397	3.010
WOMAC-S	-	-0.174	.194	1.952
CPSS-PC	-	0.148	.161	1.218
CPSS-C	-	0.251	.053	1.859
CPSS-F	-	0.141	.195	1.294
Criterion variable: MDFRT left				
Overall Model $R^2=0.439$ Adjusted $R^2=0.424$ F= 28.610				
Predictor variables	Regression coefficient (B)	Standardized coefficient (β)	P value	VIF
CPSS-C	0.197	0.474	.001	1.859
WOMAC-PF	-0.095	-0.242	.047	1.859
Excluded variables				
VAS (mm)	-	0.022	.821	1.215
WOMAC-P	-	0.154	.316	3.028
WOMAC-S	-	-0.100	.419	1.956
CPSS-PC	-	0.084	.508	2.045
CPSS-F	-	-0.061	.576	1.530

Abbreviations: CPSS-C, Chronic Pain Self-Efficacy Scale-Coping; CPSS-F, CPSS-Functionality; CPSS-PC, CPSS-Pain Control; WOMAC-P, Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index-Pain; WOMAC-PF, WOMAC-Physical Function; WOMAC-S, WOMAC-Stiffness; MDFRT, Multi-Directional Functional Reach Test; VAS, Visual Analogue Scale.